

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18053682>

Gönderiliş Tarihi: 27/09/2025

Kabul Tarihi: 25/12/2025

ORCID 0000-0001-6993-7617

TÜRKİYE’DE ENFLASYONUN DİNAMİKLERİ: FOURIER ADL EŞ BÜTÜNLEŞME TESTİNDEN KANITLAR

Bekir EREN¹

ÖZ

Bu çalışmanın amacı, Türkiye’de enflasyonu etkileyen faktörleri yapısal kırılmalı analizle ortaya koymaktır. Yöntem olarak, Fourier ADL eşbütünleşme testi, FMOLS tahmincisi ve hata düzeltme modeli kullanılarak, 2013Ç1-2025Ç2 dönemi için, enflasyonun dinamikleri araştırılmıştır. Fourier ADL eşbütünleşme testi sonuçları, enflasyon ile beklentiler ve döviz kuru arasında güçlü ve pozitif bir uzun vadeli ilişki olduğunu göstermektedir. Ancak, enflasyon ile ücret göstergeleri ve TCMB fonlama oranı arasında anlamlı bir uzun vadeli ilişki bulunamamıştır. Tahmin edilen uzun dönemli eşbütünleşme katsayıları da beklentilerin ve döviz kurunun enflasyon üzerinde güçlü ve pozitif bir etkiye sahip olduğunu ortaya koymuştur. Hata düzeltme modeli sonuçları da söz konusu uzun dönemli ilişkiyi doğrularken, kısa vadede de beklentilerin ve döviz kurunun enflasyonun belirleyicisi olduğunu göstermektedir. Bunların yanında, beklentilerin daha güçlü bir etkiye sahip olduğu bulunmuştur. Ayrıca, 2021 yılı sonundan itibaren uygulanan alışılmadık para politikaları enflasyonu pozitif etkilerken, 2023 ikinci yarısından itibaren yeniden fiyat istikrarına odaklanılmasının enflasyonu negatif etkilediği tespit edilmiştir. Bu çerçevede, beklentilerin yönetilmesi için güvenilir ve şeffaf politikaların uygulanmasının, para politikasının iletişiminin artırılmasının ve merkez bankasının bağımsızlığının güçlendirilmesinin enflasyon ile mücadelede faydalı olacağı değerlendirilmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Fourier ADL, Yapısal Kırılmalar, Beklentiler, Enflasyon.

Jel Kodu: E31, E52, E58, E60.

DYNAMICS OF INFLATION IN TURKEY: EVIDENCE FROM FOURIER ADL COINTEGRATION TEST

ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to reveal the factors affecting inflation in Turkey through a structural break analysis. Using the Fourier ADL cointegration test, FMOLS estimator, and error correction model, the dynamics of inflation have been investigated for the period 2013Q1-2025Q2. The Fourier ADL cointegration test results indicate a strong and positive long-term relationship between inflation, expectations, and the exchange rate. However, no significant long-term relationship is found between inflation and wage indicators and the central bank funding rate. The estimated long-term cointegration coefficients also reveal that expectations and the exchange rate have a strong and positive effect on inflation. The error correction model results confirm this long-term relationship and show that expectations and the exchange rate are determinants of inflation also in the short term. Moreover, expectations have stronger impact. Furthermore, while the unconventional monetary policies implemented since the end of 2021 have positively impacted inflation, the renewed focus on price stability since the second half of 2023 has negatively impacted inflation. In this context, implementing reliable and transparent policies to manage expectations, increasing the communication of monetary policy, and strengthening the independence of the central bank may be beneficial in combating inflation.

Keywords: Fourier ADL, Structural Breaks, Expectations, Inflation.

Jel Codes: E31, E52, E58, E60.

¹ Assistant Professor, Ankara Medipol University, Faculty of Economics, Administrative and Social Sciences, erenbekir@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

Inflation negatively impacts those who cannot adjust their incomes to change in price level and fixed income groups by reducing their purchasing power. It also has negative consequences for creditors in debt transactions, reduces confidence for national currency, decreases the government tax revenue, and discourages new investments by increasing uncertainty (Ball, 1992:371; Sugözü and Yaşar, 2020). Considering the damage inflation causes to the economy, achieving price stability represents a significant gain for countries.

Inflation has been one of the most significant problems facing the Turkish economy for many periods. Following the high inflation period of the 1990s, monetary policies focused on price stability and granting instrument independence to the Central Bank of the Republic of Türkiye (CBRT) reduced it to single digits in the early 2000s. However, after 2017, structural problems and the implemented economic policies led to a resurgence of inflation. Since the last quarter of 2021, the CBRT's unconventional monetary policy has led to inflation spiraling out of control. Identifying the dynamics of the period when inflation began reaching double digits in Türkiye will guide policymakers and be beneficial in preventing the repetition of past mistakes.

In the literature, money supply, interest rates, exchange rates, and oil prices are frequently used to explain the inflation in Türkiye (Özkök, 2021; Kolcu, 2023). Also, a few studies include expectations and wages (Göcen, 2020; Torun et al., 2024; Saatçioğlu, 2005; Korkmaz, 2017). The studies usually employed traditional cointegration analyses, causality tests, ADRL and NARDL methods. There are a limited number of studies that consider structural breaks (Mohanty and John, 2015, Göcen, 2020).

The aim of this study is to reveal the inflation dynamics in Türkiye for the period 2013Q1-2025Q2, considering structural breaks in the economy. This study differs from previous studies by examining the impact of the monetary policy shift between 2021Q4 and 2023Q2 on inflation for the first time, which led to significant structural breaks in the Turkish economy. During the unusual monetary policy period, Turkish economy experienced an unprecedented jump in inflation. Therefore, it is important to include this period in empirical analysis. In addition, the study introduces a significant innovation by using the Fourier ADL (FADL) cointegration test with structural breaks for the first time in national literature to explain the dynamics of inflation. Also, the FMOLS estimator and error correction model are used to estimate the short- and long-term effects of explanatory variables. Furthermore, it appears that existing studies do not adequately employ expectations and wages. Another contribution of this study is the inclusion of expectations, minimum wage and average wage into the empirical analysis and the use of the CBRT funding rate, which is the most important indicator of monetary policy, instead of deposit and credit interest rate.

The first section of the study explains the purpose, methodology, and contribution to the literature. The second section presents the theoretical framework for inflation through a literature review and then summarizes existing empirical studies. The third section describes the study's methodology and the data. The fourth section presents the empirical analysis and shares the findings. The study is completed with conclusions and recommendations.

2. LITREATURE REVIEW

Inflation, defined as a continuous increase in the general price level, has many causes. Inflation is generally explained through supply-side factors, demand-side factors, and expectations. Demand-pull inflation occurs when the aggregate demand for goods and services increases faster than supply. A rapid rise in the money supply is a significant factor that accelerates investment and consumption expenditures, putting upward pressure on prices. Cost-push inflation occurs when production costs increase due to rising commodity prices such as oil and food, rising labor costs, increased tax burdens on companies, and natural disasters. In these cases, aggregate supply decreases while the general price level rises. When the economy is highly dependent on imports, a rise in exchange rates also leads to inflation through the cost

channel. Finally, the expectation of consumers and producers that prices will continue to rise in the future is another factor. These expectations increase workers' wage demands and firms' costs. Consequently, the rise in the cost of goods and services is passed on to consumers as higher prices (CBRT, 2004). In addition to these channels, rising financing costs for small and medium-sized companies with high financing dependence also puts upward pressure on prices.

Schools of economics explain the causes of inflation using different approaches. Classical economists, using the quantity theory of money, define inflation as a monetary phenomenon. Increase in the money supply is the primary cause of inflation. Keynes (1936) attempted to explain price increases employing the concept of an inflationary gap. The Keynesian approach focuses on the demand side of the economy and assumes that prices and wages are rigid in the short run. As the economy approaches full employment, inflationary pressure begins to increase alongside the increase in demand. When production exceeds potential levels, price increases arise due to the impact of wages and employment. In parallel with the classical approach, the monetarist approach also views inflation as a monetary phenomenon. The rapid rise in money supply beyond production creates an inflationary effect. While an increase in the money supply may increase production in the short term, it only increases prices in the long run. Monetary policy must be regulated to control inflation (Friedman, 1956). Keynesian and Monetarist approaches assert that individuals possess adaptive expectations to anticipate changes in the general price level. Adaptive expectations refer to future expectations being considered as an average of past changes. According to this approach, future price levels are shaped by the price levels of previous periods (Ekelund and Tollison, 1986: 687-688).

Vazquez (1956) attempts to explain inflation through structural factors in addition to monetary developments. Focusing on supply-side factors, this approach argues that rising input costs and devaluations lead to inflation. Production fluctuations and vulnerabilities in the agricultural sector affect inflation through the cost and supply channels. Conversely, in economies with high dependence on imports of raw materials and intermediate goods, significant price increases occur because of deterioration in the external balance and depreciation of the national currency. Chronic budget deficits and their financing methods can also trigger inflation (Canavese, 1982; Yüksel, 2013; Kolcu, 2023).

Neoclassical economists, maintaining the assumption of flexible prices and wages in the Classical school, argue that the rational expectations and imperfect information of economic actors influence inflation. Rational expectations refer to making predictions about the future using all available information. Behavior of the economic actors alter the expected outcomes. According to this approach, individuals do not make systematic errors because they have complete information about the effects of economic policies. While in the short term unexpected expansionary monetary and fiscal policies may temporarily affect real variables, in the long term only general price level increase owing to rational expectations. On the other hand, expected expansionary policies only lead to inflation in both the short and long term. This approach links monetary expansion to inflation and also addresses the role of expectations (Muth, 1961; Sargent, 1976).

New Keynesian economists developed the missing micro foundations and supply-side perspective of the Keynesian approach. While accepting rational expectations, they assumed that wages and prices were rigid in the short run due to collective bargaining agreements and imperfect competition. Therefore, in the short run, expansionary monetary policy can affect real variables and not lead to inflation. However, in the long run, rise in the money supply increase the general price level thanks to flexible prices and wages (Gordon, 1990).

Employing these theoretical approaches, the relationship between inflation and macroeconomic indicators has been investigated. The relationship between inflation and interest rates is often discussed within the framework of the Fisher hypothesis, the Neo-Fisher hypothesis, and the Taylor rule. The Fisher hypothesis claims that there is a positive link between the nominal interest rate and the expected inflation rate, implying that these rates should move in harmony. Accordingly, there is a general acceptance that

inflation is the cause of interest rates, and short-term interest rates are effectively used to combat inflation. On the contrary, the Neo-Fisher hypothesis, which argues that interest rates are the cause of inflation in the long run, has also gained support (Tayyar, 2019:307; Ioana, 2017:578). It claims that a long-term low nominal interest rate reduces long-term expected inflation while also leading to a decrease in current inflation. On the other hand, a long-term high nominal interest rate leads to an increase in inflation (Sümer, 2020:3; Williamson, 2016:8).

Taylor (1993) also provided an important theoretical framework. Taylor's rule argues that monetary policy should be implemented based on rules, suggesting that the central bank should alter the nominal interest rate in line with the change in inflation (Williamson, 2016:8). Short-term interest rates are determined by considering the level of inflation and output. When inflation and output level deviates from the target value, central banks adjust the policy interest rate.

The level of the minimum wage and other wages can impact inflation through both the input cost and demand channels. It is argued that the minimum wage is a significant cost driver, particularly for small and medium-sized firms. A study of CBRT indicates that 10% increase in the minimum wage affects inflation by 0.8% to 1.2% annually. The impact of the minimum wage on costs varies depending on the labor intensity of sectors. Wage costs constitute approximately 7% of the value of production in industry, 9% in construction, and 18% in services (CBRT, 2023). Therefore, the minimum wage is not considered the primary determinant of input costs. However, a rise in the minimum wage supports growth by increasing aggregate demand. While some inflationary risks arise through the cost channel in the short term, it leads to increases in private sector turnover and tax revenues in the medium and long term (Coviello et al., 2022). Furthermore, in developing countries like Türkiye, the minimum wage level appears to be only sufficient to meet basic needs (Akgül, 2016). Therefore, it seems unrealistic to argue that the minimum wage will lead to demand-pull inflation. On the other hand, there are studies showing that rising real wages increase labor productivity and do not lead to a decline in employment (Millea and Fuess, 2005; Barth et al., 2020; Taymaz et al., 2024). A reasonable minimum wage facilitates families' access to education and healthcare and supports human capital and growth in the long run (Özer and Gülşen, 2024). Suppressing the minimum wage may lead to a vicious cycle of low wages and low productivity.

Recent analyses for Türkiye indicate that exchange rates and expectations have much stronger effects on inflation than wages. Also, past inflation has an important impact on expectations (CBRT, 2023 and 2024). Expectations have become more important in explaining inflation with the advent of monetarist economists in the 1950s. It has been argued that improper management of expectations would lead to high inflation (Phelps, 1967; Friedman, 1968). In Türkiye, household and real sector price expectations are closely monitored to control inflation. Moreover, in developing countries with high exchange rate pass-through, exchange rate changes alter the domestic price level (Mundell, 1963; Miller, 1992). While exchange rates primarily affect domestic prices through the prices of imported goods, this impact extends to consumer prices. These changes in domestic prices have indirect and secondary effects on real incomes, consumption expenditures, and trade flows (Mauro et al, 2008). Türkiye experiences high exchange rate pass-through during crisis periods, and the exchange rate, through imported goods and expectations, influences the prices of many goods and services.

An examination of the empirical literature reveals that variables such as money supply, interest rates, exchange rates, and oil prices are frequently used to explain the inflation in Türkiye. A summary of existing empirical studies is presented in Table 1. Accordingly, a few studies include expectations and wages. These studies mostly utilize traditional cointegration analyses and causality tests. Furthermore, the ADRL and NARDL methods are frequently used. Moreover, there are a limited number of studies that consider structural breaks and there is no study using the Fourier approach to analyze the determinants of inflation.

Table 1. Empiric Studies in Literature

Author(s)	Country	Period	Method	Variables	Findings
Saatçioğlu (2005)	Türkiye	1988:01-2004:05	Johansen cointegration test	Inflation, exchange rate, domestic credit, interest rate and wage	There is long-run link between inflation and exchange rate, domestic credit, interest rate and wage.
Gül and Ekinci (2006)	Türkiye	1984:01-2003:12	Johansen cointegration and Granger causality test	Inflation, exchange rate	One-way causality from exchange to inflation in the long run.
Altıntaş et al. (2008)	Türkiye	1992:01-2006:12	ARDL	Inflation, M2 money supply and budget deficit	There is a positive link between inflation and money supply in short-run and long-run.
Yılandı (2010)	Türkiye	1989:01-2008:01	KSS and Engle-Granger cointegration test	Inflation, interest rate	There is no long-run link between inflation and interest rate.
Doğan et al. (2015)	Türkiye	2003:02-2015:02	Johansen cointegration and Granger causality test	Inflation, interest rate	There is no long-run link between inflation and interest rate. Inflation affects interest rate in short run.
Taban and Şengür (2016)	Türkiye	2003:02-2014:12	VAR block Granger causality test, impulse-response analysis	Inflation, interest rate	There is no relationship between inflation and interest rate.
Korkmaz (2017)	Türkiye	1998:01-2015:04	OLS	Inflation, deposit interest rate, real exchange rate, economic growth, real domestic credit, wage	Deposit interest rate affects the inflation both in short and long run. Real exchange rate has an impact on inflation in short run. Growth affects inflation in long run.
Afsal et al. (2018)	Türkiye	2004:01-2018:05	NARDL	Money supply, exchange rate, interest rate	There is long-run link between inflation and interest rate, money supply, exchange rate.
Kılavuz and Altınöz (2020)	Türkiye	2006:4Q-2018:4Q	ARDL	Inflation, money supply, exchange rate, interest rate	There is weak and positive relationship between inflation and interest rate, and money supply in long run.
Göcen (2020)	Türkiye	2005:01-2020:09	Engle-Granger cointegration test, Toda-Yamamoto and Hatemi-J asymmetric causality test	Inflation, expectations	There is a bilateral positive link between the expectations and inflation.
Özkök (2021)	Türkiye	2003:02-2021:07	ARDL and Toda-Yamamoto causality test	Inflation, interest rate, real exchange rate, money supply	There is negative long-run link between inflation and real exchange rate.

Tuğral and Bari (2021)	Türkiye	2003Q1-2020Q1	ARDL and NARDL	Inflation, exchange rate	While the exchange rate affects the short and long term, the long-term effects are stronger.
Varlık and Varlık (2021)	Türkiye	2010:10-2021:03	NARDL	Inflation, central bank credibility	In the long run, the rise in central bank credibility reduces inflation, while the drop increases it. It has been found that decreases in credibility have a much stronger effect on inflation than increases.
Akçağlayan and Gemicioğlu (2022)	Türkiye	1998Q1-2019Q4	NARDL	CPI and PPI inflation, oil prices	The increases in oil prices cause a rise in consumer and producer inflation but decreases either do not affect inflation or have a relatively small effect.
Kolcu (2023)	Türkiye	2006-2021	Stepwise Regression, VAR, ARDL	Inflation, exchange rate, real money supply, interest rate, budget deficit, current account deficit	Exchange rate affects inflation positively both in short and long run. Real money supply has a negative impact on inflation. Budget deficit affects inflation only in the short run. Interest rate has a weak positive impact.
Torun et al. (2024)	Türkiye	2016-2024	ARDL	Inflation, expectations, money supply	Money supply has a significant impact on inflation in the long run. Expectations affect inflation in the short run.
Yantur (2025)	Türkiye	2015:1-2024:11	ARDL	Inflation, exchange rate, expectations, real interest rate, brent oil, real interest rate	Exchange rate, brent oil and real interest rate affect inflation both in short and long run. Households' expectations only affect inflation in the long run.
Ersin (2025)	Türkiye	2011:01-2023:12	Hacker and Hatemi-J symmetric and Hatemi-J asymmetric causality test	Inflation, BİST100 index, reel exchange rate, real money supply, gold prices	All independent variables are cause of inflation.
Greenidge and DaCosta (2009)	Caribbean countries	1970-2006	ARDL, VECM	Inflation, unemployment, brent oil, exchange rate, expectations	Changes in oil prices, exchange rates and interest rates are effective on inflation. Interest rates are negatively effective in the long term.
Khan and Gill (2010)	Pakistan	1970-2007	OLS	Consumer price index, exchange rate, interest rate, agricultural support prices, import, rate, agricultural support prices	Exchange rate, import and agricultural support prices positively affect inflation.
Nguyen et al (2012)	Vietnam	2001-2009	OLS, Granger causality test, VAR	Inflation, money supply, exchange rate, interest rate, oil price, price of rice, prices in manufacturing	Previous period inflation, money supply and external cost shocks are main determinants of inflation. The effect of output, exchange rate and interest rates on inflation is weaker.

Alimi (2012)	Nigeria	1960-2009	Johansen cointegration and Granger causality test	Consumer price index, real wage, interest rate, money supply	One-way causality from money supply to inflation
Kim and Lee (2013)	Asian countries	2005:12-2012:04	Impulse-response analysis	Inflation, expectations	Inflation expectations play an important role in actual inflation.
Mohanty and John (2015)	India	1996-2014	SVAR	Inflation, oil price, petrol, output gap, Budget deficit, interest rate	The main determinants of inflation are the budget deficit and oil prices.
Xu et al. (2017)	US	1978:01-2015:11	Granger causality test and rolling-window	Inflation, expectations	A two-way causality relationship between inflation and expectations.
Madito and Odhiambo (2018)	South Africa	1970-2015	ECM	Inflation, expectations, money supply, government spending, real exchange rate, real GDP, import prices, wage	Expectations, wage, government spendings and import prices affect inflation positively, while GDP and exchange rates affect negatively.
Chaudhary and Xiumin (2018)	Nepal	1975-2016	OLS	Consumer price index, expectations, money supply, real GDP, inflation of India	Expectations, money supply, inflation of India affects inflation positively while real GDP has a negative impact.
Setiartiti and Hapsari (2019)	Indonesia	2010-2017	ECM	Inflation, money supply, GDP, interest rate, exchange rate	Money supply has a positive effect on inflation in the short term. Exchange rates, interest rates, and GDP do not affect inflation.
Çalışkan et al. (2021)	BRICS-T countries	2003:01-2019:12	Breitung and Candelon causality test	Inflation, oil prices	Positive oil price shocks significantly affect inflation rates in the long run. Moreover, increases in oil prices lead to persistent inflationary effects.

3.METHODOLOGY AND DATA

3.1.Methodology

In the empirical analysis methods that consider structural breaks are used because the 2013Q1-2025Q2 period encompasses significant policy changes in the Turkish economy. In this context, firstly the stationarity of the series are tested using unit root tests with structural breaks. In time series, structural breaks can occur in the constant term and/or slope at different periods. War, natural disasters, policy changes, and crises can lead to them. A study by Perron (1989) shows that ignoring structural breaks in unit root tests can yield misleading results. Various unit root tests that consider structural breaks exist in the literature. Perron (1989), Zivot-Andrews (1992), and Lee-Strazicich (2003) are cited as prominent unit root tests with structural breaks (Göçer et al., 2013). In this study, it is aimed to obtain more reliable results by using Perron and Zivot-Andrews unit root test with structural breaks.

On the other hand, structural breaks also affect the reliability of cointegration tests. Therefore, examining long-term relationships with traditional approaches such as the Johansen and Engle-Granger

cointegration tests can lead to misleading results. There are new generation cointegration tests that also consider structural breaks. Gregory and Hansen (1996) first developed a cointegration test that allows for a single structural break. This approach examines three separate models: structural break in the constant term, structural break in the trend and constant term, and regime change. Hatemi-J (2008) redesigned the three models to consider a maximum of two structural breaks. However, the results of these tests are not reliable when the number of structural breaks is large. Furthermore, pre-determined structural breaks can lead to misleading outcomes. Banerjee et al. (2017) created a new cointegration test by adding Fourier functions to the Banerjee et al. (1998) cointegration test to consider a large number of structural breaks. They developed the Fourier ADL (FADL) cointegration test that includes structural breaks internally. In this test, slowly and gradually occurring breaks are included in the model by means of sine and cosine functions. In addition, in analyses involving Fourier functions, the date, number, and shapes of structural breaks are not important, and there is no predetermined structural break (Yılancı et al., 2020). Banerjee et al. The Fourier ADL model of (2017) is shown in equation (1).

$$\Delta y_t = d(t) + \beta_1 y_{t-1} + \gamma' x_{t-1} + \emptyset' \Delta x_t + u_t \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

$$d(t) = a_0 + \gamma_1 \sin\left(\frac{2\pi kt}{T}\right) + \gamma_2 \cos\left(\frac{2\pi kt}{T}\right) \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

In the equation $d(t)$ is the deterministic term. The lagged values of the variables have been added to the model to correct the autocorrelation problem. Equation 2 is substituted in the equation 1 and the final equation is obtained. In the equation “ k ” is frequency, “ t ” is trend and “ T ” is the total number of observations. While the null hypothesis suggests that there is no long-term relationship between variables ($\beta_1 = 0$), alternative hypothesis suggests that there is a long-term relationship between variables ($\beta_1 < 0$). Long-term relationship is tested using critical values produced by Banerjee et al. (2017) (Yılancı et al., 2020; Özbek and Naimoğlu, 2022). Thus, to overcome the shortcomings of traditional approaches, this study examines the long-term relationship between variables with the new generation cointegration test FADL.

In addition, fully modified ordinary least square (FMOLS) estimator, developed by Fillips and Hansen (1990), is employed to predict the long-term cointegration coefficients and the short-term coefficients and the error correction model. The FMOLS estimator, which resolves diagnostic problems in traditional estimates, considers endogeneity, heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation problems by using robust standard errors. In addition, this approach produces reliable estimates for small sample size (Chen and Huang, 2013: 51). The estimated error correction model with FMOLS shows the adjustment between variables in the short term and it enables the evaluation of long-term relationships.

3.2.Data

To explain inflation dynamics in Türkiye, an empirical analysis has been done using quarterly data for the period 2013Q1-2025Q2. In addition to the exchange rate and interest rate, which are frequently used in the literature, the study also includes expectations and various wage indicators. The CBRT weighted average funding cost, which provides important signals about the monetary policy stance, is used as a proxy for the interest rate. While deposit and loan interest rates are used in studies in the literature, this study employs the CBRT funding rate for the first time. The CBRT funding rate gives the most accurate signal for the stance of monetary policy. The deposit and loan interest rates may be affected by bank behaviors and expectations; therefore, they may not be a good proxy for the monetary policy changes. Moreover, different wage indicators have been used for the first time to measure the demand and supply-side impact of wages on inflation. Furthermore, because the examined period includes significant policy shifts and structural breaks, these effects are reflected to the model with dummy variables. Information on the dependent and independent variables used in the study is provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Description of Variables Used in Empirical Analysis

Variable	Explanation	Source
Inflation	Annual percentage change of consumer price index	CBRT
Expectations	Annual CPI Inflation expectations for the next 12 months	CBRT
Exchange rate	Value of 1 US dollar against Turkish Lira	CBRT
Funding Rate	CBRT weighted average funding cost	CBRT
MW	Minimum wage rate announced by government	Ministry of Labor and Social Security
Average wage	Ratio of total income to total employment	TURKSTAT
MW/Average wage	Ratio of minimum wage to average rate	TURKSTAT, Ministry of Labor and Social Security
Dummy1	The impact of unconventional monetary policies implemented between 2021:Q4 and 2025:Q2	Author's calculations
Dummy2	The impact of return to conventional monetary policies since 2023:Q2	Author's calculations

4. EMPIRICAL STUDY AND FINDINGS

4.1. Unit Root Test

Perron and Zivot-Andrews unit root tests, which consider structural breaks, are used to test the stationarity of the time series. The results are presented in Table 3. The Perron unit root test indicates that the null hypothesis is rejected at the 1% level for the first differences of all variables except the inflation and funding rate, and that the series is stationary. The first differences of the inflation and funding rate variables are stationary at the 5% level. Also, Zivot-Andrews test results confirm that all variables are stationary at the 1% level for their first differences. Thus, the results indicate that all variables are non-stationary at their level but stationary in their first differences.

Table 3. Unit Root Test Results

	Perron Unit Root Test				Zivot-Andrews Unit Root Test	
	Level		First Difference		First Difference	
	Statistic Value	Breaking Date	Statistic Value	Breaking Date	Statistic Value	Breaking Date
Inflation	-3.3879	2020Q2	-5.7772	2022Q1	-5.5266	2022Q4
Expectations	-4.0082	2021Q3	-6.9149	2022Q2	-6.0148	2022Q3
Exchange rate	-1.6447	2021Q4	-6.8083	2021Q3	-6.9558	2021Q4
Funding rate	-3.6474	2023Q4	-5.3239	2023Q1	-5.4038	2023Q2

Average wage	-4.1445	2021Q2	-13.8243	2022Q4	-6.0439	2023Q1
Minimum wage	-1.4062	2022Q2	-12.4429	2022Q4	-9.3227	2023Q1
Minimum wage / Average wage	-1.5711	2023Q4	-7.9220	2016Q1	-7.8443	2016Q1

Note: Threshold values for Perron test are -5.92, -5.23, and -4.92 for the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. Threshold values for Zivot-Andrews test are -5.34, -4.93, and -4.58 for the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively.

4.2. Cointegration Test

After determining that the time series are stationary in their first differences, a cointegration test is conducted to investigate the existence of a long-run relationship between inflation and the explanatory variables. The critical value in the FADL cointegration test with structural breaks varies depending on the number of variables and frequency. According to the test results, a long-run relationship is found between inflation and expectations at the 1% level, while a long-run relationship is demonstrated between inflation and the exchange rate at the 5% level (Table 4). These findings are consistent with the results of studies using traditional methods in the literature. On the other hand, the outcomes with structural breaks indicate that there is no significant long-run relationship between inflation and the funding rate, the minimum wage, the average wage, and the ratio of the minimum wage to the average wage. In this study, the CBRT funding rate is used for the interest rate, while previous studies introduced deposit and loan interest rates. However, the findings are consistent and implies that Fisher and Neo-Fisher hypothesis are not valid for the examined period. The lack of a significant long-term relationship between inflation and the funding rate can be interpreted as indicating that interest rates have a short-term impact on inflation. Furthermore, the CBRT funding rate may have a greater impact on inflation through expectations and exchange rate channel indirectly. The insignificant long-term relationship between inflation and various wage indicators, however, differs from many former empirical studies. This outcome may indicate that wage increases increase firms' productivity rather than their costs as suggested by Millea and Fuess (2005) and Taymaz et al. (2024). Furthermore, the results imply that average wages and the minimum wage in Türkiye, remaining at low levels, are far from generating demand-pull inflation.

Table 4. FADL Cointegration Results for Inflation and Explanatory Variables

Variables	Frequency	Test Statistic	Lag Length	
			DY	DX
Expectations	3	-4.319***	1	1
Exchange rate	1	-4.207**	1	3
Funding rate	1	-3.175	1	1
Average wage	1	-3.205	1	1
Minimum wage	1	-3.191	1	1
Minimum wage / Average wage	1	-3.326	1	1

Note: For Fourier ADL cointegration, ** indicates significance at the 5% level, and *** sign indicates significance at the 1% level.

Expectations and exchange rates, which yielded significant results, are included in the model together, and a FADL test is estimated again. The result confirms the long-term relationship between the variables at the 5% level (Table 5).

Table 5. FADL Cointegration Results for Inflation, Expectations and Exchange Rate

Variables	Frequency	Test Statistic	Lag Length		
			DY	DX	DW

Expectations and Exchange rate 3 -3.967** 3 1 1

Note: For Fourier ADL cointegration, ** indicates significance at the 5% level.

When performing the FADL test, where expectations and exchange rates are included in the model together, the equation in Table 6 is estimated. The significance of the cosine/sine variables in the model indicates the presence of structural breaks.

Table 6. FADL Cointegration Equation

Dependent Variable: D. Inflation				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	T-Statistic	Prob.
Constant	-3.004113	2.375996	-1.264359	0.2145
Inflation(-1)	-1.053182	0.265480	-3.967079	0.0003
Expectations(-1)	1.538949	0.481858	3.193779	0.0030
Exchange rate(-1)	0.245858	0.314470	0.781818	0.4396
D.Expectations(-1)	-0.304286	0.467989	-0.650200	0.5198
D.Inflation(-1)	0.424762	0.199244	2.131870	0.0401
D.Inflation(-2)	0.152200	0.172678	0.881407	0.3841
D.Inflation(-3)	0.410219	0.201690	2.033904	0.0496
D.Exchange rate(-1)	2.958316	2.067612	1.430789	0.1614
Cosine	1.833542	1.592129	1.151629	0.2573
Sine	2942081	1434301	2051230	0.0478

4.3. Estimation of Long-Term Cointegration Coefficients

Based on the FADL test results, long-term cointegration coefficients are estimated using the FMOLS estimator. First, a model incorporating expectations and the exchange rate is estimated (Equation 3). Then separate models are estimated for expectations and the exchange rate, and dummy variables representing structural breaks are added to the models (Equations 4 and 5).

$$\text{Inflation}_t = B_0 + B_1\text{Expectations}_t + B_2\text{Exchangerate}_t + u_t \quad (\text{Equation 3})$$

$$\text{Inflation}_t = B_0 + B_1\text{Expectations}_t + B_2\text{Dummy1}_t + B_3\text{Dummy2}_t + u_t \quad (\text{Equation 4})$$

$$\text{Inflation}_t = B_0 + B_1\text{Exchangerate}_t + B_2\text{Dummy1}_t + B_3\text{Dummy2}_t + u_t \quad (\text{Equation 5})$$

Estimation results for different models are presented below (Tables 7, 8, and 9). The Newey-West method is used to correct heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation problems. In the model where the two variables are used together, expectations have a positive and significant effect on inflation, while the exchange rate is insignificant (Table 7). When the effects of expectations and the exchange rate are examined in different models, both variables have a positive and significant effect on inflation in the long run (Table 8 and Table 9). However, the effect of expectations is stronger. Furthermore, dummy variables indicating significant changes in monetary policy have also a significant impact on inflation. Dummy variable 1, representing the unconventional monetary policy implemented during the 2021Q4-2023Q2 period, has a positive and strong effect on inflation, while dummy variable 2, representing the return to conventional monetary policy focused on inflation targeting after 2023Q2, has a strong and negative effect on inflation. The results imply that unconventional monetary policy has contributed to the out-of-control inflation in Türkiye in recent years. Conversely, monetary policy prioritizing price stability has also significantly contributed to the decline in inflation.

Table 7. Results of Equation 1

Dependent Variable: Inflation			
Variables	Coefficient	T Statistic	Prob.
Expectations	1.902***	10.769	0.000
Exchange rate	0.051	0.281	0.780
Constant	-6.358***	-3.163	0.003

Note: *** indicates significance at the 1% level.

Table 8. Results of Equation 2

Dependent Variable: Inflation			
Variables	Coefficient	T Statistic	Prob.
Expectations	1.893***	54.366	0.000
Dummy1	7.118***	6.497	0.000
Dummy2	-15.451***	-6.300	0.000
Constant	-6.341***	-10.481	0.000

Note: *** indicates significance at the 1% level.

Table 9. Results of Equation 3

Dependent Variable: Inflation			
Variables	Coefficient	T Statistic	Prob.
Exchange rate	1.250***	7.110	0.000
Dummy1	3.925***	7.175	0.000
Constant	7.613***	2.827	0.007

Note: *** indicates significance at the 1% level.

4.4.Short-Term Analysis and Error Correction Model

In variables with significant long-term relationships, some deviations from the equilibrium relationship may occur due to dynamic behavior. This is a key difference of cointegration equations, and it affects short-term dynamics. The imbalance between short-term and long-term effects in time series is eliminated through the error correction model (ECM), a dynamic model. For the error correction mechanism to work, the error correction term in the estimated model must have a significant and negative coefficient. If these conditions are met, a reliable long-term relationship emerges. The error correction model is constructed based on the estimated model for the long-term coefficients. For this model to be reliable, all independent variables in the long-term model must be significant. Therefore, different models are estimated for expectations and the exchange rate. The equation of the error correction model obtained using Equations 4 and 5 is written as follows.

$$\Delta \text{Inflation}_t = B_0 + \Delta B_1 \text{Expectations}_t + \text{ECM}_{(-1)} + u_t \quad (\text{Equation 6})$$

$$\Delta \text{Inflation}_t = B_0 + \Delta B_1 \text{Exchangerate}_t + \text{ECM}_{(-1)} + u_t \quad (\text{Equation 7})$$

Tables 10 and 11 present the findings of the error correction models obtained using equations 4 and 5. The results show that the ECM(-1) variable is negative and significant at the 1% level in all estimated equations. This confirms the existence of a significant long-term relationship between inflation and expectations, exchange rate. The coefficient of ECM(-1) indicates the extent to which deviations from long-term values are corrected in the subsequent period. Furthermore, the statistical significance of

expectations in Table 9 and exchange rate in Table 11 indicates that they have a significant and positive impact on inflation in the short term. However, expectations appear to have a statistically stronger significance level.

Table 10. Error Correction Model Results for Equation 6

Dependent Variable: D(Inflation)			
Variables	Coefficient	T Statistic	Prob.
D(Expectations)	1.409***	9.011	0.000
ECM(-1)	-0.592***	-6.501	0.000
Constant	0.103	0.188	0.852

Note: *** indicates significance at the 1% level.

Table 11. Error Correction Model Results for Equation 7

Dependent Variable: D(Inflation)			
Variables	Coefficient	T Statistic	Prob.
D(Exchange rate)	1.641*	1.899	0.064
ECM(-1)	-0.342***	-3.701	0.001
Constant	0.867	-0.723	0.473

Note: * indicates significance at the 10% level, *** indicates significance at the 1% level.

Findings of empirical study confirm theoretical approach of Phelps (1967) and Friedman (1968) in terms of the role of the expectations on inflation. In addition, exchange rate has an important factor on inflation as Mundell (1963) and Miller (1992) claimed.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The period 2013Q1-2025Q2, when inflation in Türkiye was on an upward trend, has been examined using a structural break analysis. FADL cointegration test results indicate a strong and positive long-term relationship between inflation, expectations, and the exchange rate. However, no significant long-term relationship is found between inflation and wage indicators and the CBRT funding rate. Based on the cointegration test, the short- and long-term effects of expectations and exchange rate on inflation have been examined in detail using the FMOLS estimator and the error correction model. Findings suggest that expectations have a stronger impact on inflation in the long term than the exchange rate. An increase in expected inflation positively affects current inflation. Error correction model results also confirm the long-term effects of expectations and exchange rate on inflation. In the short term, expectations and exchange rate also have a positive and significant effect. However, the significance level of expectations is higher than that of the exchange rate. Furthermore, dummy variables formed for changes in monetary policy have a significant effect on inflation. The dummy variable generated for the 2021Q4-2025Q2 period seems to have a positive effect on inflation. This result implies that unconventional monetary policy practices have driven inflation out of control. The dummy variable 2, representing the return to conventional monetary policy after 2023Q2, has a negative effect on inflation. This suggests that monetary policy focused on inflation targeting is effective in the disinflation process.

Empirical analysis results indicate that inflation expectations are the strongest determinant of current inflation. The results are consistent with the theoretical and empirical literature (Friedman, 1968; Miller, 1992; Madito and Odhiambo, 2018; Göcen, 2020; Tuğral and Bari 2021; Kolcu, 2023). On the other hand, this study introduces that expectations affect the inflation both in short-run and long-run in Türkiye while the link is valid only in short-run according to Torun et al. (2024) and only in long-run according to Yantur (2025). The difference may stem from the methods; these studies do not consider the

structural breaks in their models. On the other hand, this study indicates that there is not a long-term relationship between inflation and the CBRT funding rate. It is parallel to outcomes of Özkok (2021) and Taban and Şengür (2016) although they use market interest rate instead of the CBRT funding rate. However, Kılavuz and Altınöz (2020) and Kolcu (2023) find a weak link between inflation and interest rate, and Korkmaz (2017) indicates a strong link between these variables. Employing the deposit interest rate which is not a good proxy for monetary policy stance and including different periods and methods may lead to these outcomes. Furthermore, no significant long-term relationship between inflation and wage indicators support the outcomes of Korkmaz (2017) while it differs from Saatçioğlu (2005) that demonstrates the positive long-run link. Saatçioğlu (2005) uses hourly wage in the manufacturing industry as a wage indicator while this study employed minimum wage and average wage in Türkiye which are stronger proxies for wage.

According to findings, expectation management is crucial in combating inflation in Türkiye. Policymakers should implement reliable and transparent policies to manage expectations, enhance communication regarding monetary policy, and strengthen the independence and credibility of the CBRT. Moreover, past inflation rates also influence expected inflation. Therefore, holistic and consistent policies are needed to prevent inflationary inertia. Sudden changes in implemented policies, short-term perspectives, and policies that are not accepted by the market should be avoided. It would be beneficial to enact legal regulations to prevent price formations from being indexed to past inflation. In this context, aligning annual increases in public receivables, taxes, fees, and fines with the CBRT's expected inflation rate should be a significant step. Furthermore, rent increases, which significantly impact inflation, should also be regulated similarly.

Future studies should employ different indicators for inflation such as the producer price index and the İstanbul Chamber of Commerce price index and then compare the results. Additionally, examining the dynamics of inflation on a sectoral basis could be beneficial.

REFERENCES

- Afsal, M. Ş., Doğan, İ., Örün, E. and Bayram, A. (2018). Enflasyonun stokastik belirleyicileri: Türkiye ekonomisi için bir NARDL yaklaşımı. *Journal of Life Economics*, 5 (4), 57-74.
- Akçağlayan, A. and Gemicioğlu, S. (2022). Petrol fiyatlarındaki değişimin tüketici ve üretici fiyatlarına asimetric geçişkenliği. *Uluslararası Yönetim İktisat ve İşletme Dergisi*, 18(1), 59–77.
- Akgül, O. (2016). Türkiye’de asgari ücretin mahzurlu alanları ve öneriler. *Hak İş Uluslararası Emek ve Toplum Dergisi*, 5(12), 96-127.
- Alimi, R. S. (2012). The quantity theory of money and its long run implications: Empirical evidence from Nigeria. *European Scientific Journal*, 8(12), 272-288. Retrieved from <http://eujournal.org/>
- Altıntaş, H., Çetintaş H. and Taban S. (2008). Türkiye’de bütçe açığı, parasal büyüme ve enflasyon arasındaki ilişkinin ekonometrik analizi: 1992-2006. *Anadolu Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 8(2), 185-208.
- Ball, L. (1992). Why does high inflation raise inflation uncertainty? *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 29(3), 371-388, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3932\(92\)90032-W](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3932(92)90032-W).
- Banerjee, A., Dolado, J. and Mestre, R. (1998). Error-correction mechanism tests for cointegration in a single-equation framework. *Journal Of Time Series Analysis*, 19(3), 267-283.
- Banerjee, P., Arčabić, V. and Lee, H. (2017). Fourier ADL cointegration test to approximate smooth breaks with new evidence from crude oil market. *Economic Modelling*, 67, 114-124.
- Barth, E., Bryson, A. and Harald, D. O. (2020). Union density effects productivity and wages. *The Economic Journal*. 130(631), 1898-1936, <https://doi.org/10.1093/ej/ueaa048>
- Canavese, A. J. (1982). The structuralist explanation in the theory of inflation. *World Development*, 10(7), 523-529. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/0305750X82900535>
- CBRT. (2004). Enflasyon. Retrieved from <https://www.tcmb.gov.tr/wps/wcm/connect/b62e1fb7-ebc1-4922-99dc-b3ba23320b9f/enflasyon.pdf?MOD=AJPERES&CACHEID=ROO>

- CBRT. (2023). Asgari ücret artışının enflasyona etkisi üzerine bir değerlendirme. *Enflasyon Raporu III*. Retrieved from https://www.tcmb.gov.tr/wps/wcm/connect/9e350e68-3d3e-44bf-8590-83cd5eb0cf78/Kutu_2.6_2023_iii..pdf?MOD=AJPERES&CACHEID=ROOTWORKSPACE-9e350e68-3d3e-44bf-8590-83cd5eb0cf78-oCmsQkM
- CBRT. (2024). Enflasyon Raporu. Retrieved from <https://www.tcmb.gov.tr/wps/wcm/connect/tr/tcmb+tr/main+menu/yayinlar/raporlar/enflasyon+raporu/>
- CBRT. (2025). EVDS. Retrieved from <https://evds2.tcmb.gov.tr/index.php?/evds/serieMarket>
- Chaudhary, S. K. and Xiumin, Li. (2018). Analysis of the determinants of inflation in Nepal. *American Journal of Economics*, 8(5), 209-212. doi: 10.5923/j.economics.20180805.01
- Chen, J. H. and Huang, Y. F. (2013). The study of the relationship between carbon dioxide (CO₂) emission and economic growth. *Journal of International and Global Economic Studies*, 6(2), 45-61.
- Coviello, D., Deserranno, E. and Persico, N. (2022). Minimum wage and individual worker productivity: Evidence from a Large US retailer. *Journal of Political Economy*, University of Chicago Press, vol. 130(9), 2315-2360.
- Çalışkan, H., Kantarcı, T. and Çevik, E. İ. (2021). Petrol fiyatları ve enflasyon arasında frekans alanında asimetrik nedensellik analizi: BRICS-T ülkeleri üzerine bir uygulama. *Gaziantep University Journal of Social Sciences*, 20(3), 1090–1111.
- Doğan, B., Eroğlu, Ö. and Değer, O. (2015). Enflasyon ve faiz oranı arasındaki nedensellik ilişkisi: Türkiye örneği. *Çankırı Karatekin Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 6, 1-21.
- Ekelund, R. B. and Tollison, R. D. (1986). *Economics*, Boston: Little, Brown, 1986.
- Ersin, İ. (2025). Türkiye’de seçilmiş finansal göstergeler ile enflasyon arasındaki asimetrik ilişkinin incelenmesi. *Business, Economics and Management Research Journal*, 8(1), 35-51. <https://doi.org/10.58308/bemarej.1630161>
- Friedman, M. (1956). *Studies in the quantity theory of money*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1956.
- Friedman, M. (1968). The role of monetary policy. *American Economic Review*, 58(1), 1-17.
- Friedman, M. (1975). *The case for a monetary rule*. M. Friedman, An Economist’s Protest, Thomas Horton, New Jersey.
- Gordon, R. J. (1990). What is new Keynesian economics? *Journal of Economic Literature*, 18, 115-1171.
- Göçer, İ., Mercan, M. and Peker, O. (2013). Kredi hacmi artışının cari açığa etkisi: çoklu yapısal kırılmalı eşbütünlük analizi. *Istanbul University Econometrics and Statistics E-Journal*, (18), 1-17.
- Greenidge, K. and DaCosta, D. (2009). Determinants of inflation in selected Caribbean countries. *Business, Finance & Economics in Emerging Economies*, 4(2), 371-397. https://certnet.com/files/publications/journal/2009_2_4/371-397.pdf
- Gregory, A. W. and Hansen, B. E. (1996). Residual-Based tests for cointegration in models with regime shifts. *Journal of Econometrics*, 70(1), 99-126.
- Gül, E. and Ekinci, A. (2006). Türkiye’de enflasyon ve döviz kuru arasındaki nedensellik ilişkisi: 1984-2003. *Anadolu Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 6 (1), 91-106.
- Hatemi-J, A. (2008). Tests for cointegration with two unknown regime shifts with an application to financial market integration. *Empirical Economics*, 35(3), 497-505.
- Ioana, P. (2017). Monetary policy and inflation: is there a Neo-Fisher effect? Evidence from inflation targeting countries in central and eastern Europe. *Ovidius University Annals, Economic Sciences Series*, 17(1), 578-583.
- Keynes, J. M. (1936). *The general theory of employment, Interest and Money*. London: Macmillan.
- Khan, R. E. A. and Gill, A. R. (2010). Determinants of inflation: a case of Pakistan (1970-2007). *Journal of Economics*, 1(1), 45-51, Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/32122029>
- Kılavuz, E. and Altınöz, B. (2020). Türkiye’de para arzı ile enflasyon arasındaki ilişki: ARDL sınır testi yaklaşımı. *Ekonomi, Politika & Finans Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 5(2), 242-260.
- Kim, J. I. and Lee., J. (2013). How Important are inflation expectations in driving Asian inflation? *BIS Papers*, Chapters 70, 41-63.
- Kolcu, F. (2023). Türkiye’de enflasyonun belirleyicileri. *Hitit Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 16(1), 31-56. doi:10.17218/hititsbd.1207652
- Korkmaz, Ö. (2017). Enflasyon oranını etkileyen faktörlerin belirlenmesi: Türkiye üzerine bir uygulama. *Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 32(2), 109-142.

- Lee, J. and Strazicich, M. C. (2003). Minimum Lagrange multiplier unit root test with two structural breaks. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 85(4), 1082-1089.
- Madito, O. and Odhiambo, N. M. (2018). The main determinants of inflation in South Africa: an empirical investigation. *Organizations and Markets in Emerging Economies*, 9(2), 212-232. doi:1015388/omee.2018.10.00011
- Mauro, D. F., Ruffer, R. and Bunda, I. (2008). The changing role of the exchange rate in a globalized economy. *ECB Occasional Paper series*, No:94. <https://www.ecb.europa.eu/pub/pdf/scpops/ecbocp94.pdf>
- Millea, M. and Fuess, M. S. (2005). Does pay affect productivity or react to it? Examination of U.S. manufacturing. *The Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance*, 45(4), 796-807. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.qref.2004.06.004>.
- Miller, M. H. (1992). Exchange rate changes and the impact on domestic prices. *Journal of International Economics*, 32(3–4), 169–193. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1996\(92\)90030-M](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1996(92)90030-M).
- Mohanty, D. and John, J. (2015). Determinants of inflation in India. *Journal of Asian Economics*, 36, 86-96. doi: 10.1016/j.asieco.2014.08.002
- Mundell, R. A. (1963). Capital mobility and stabilization policy under fixed and flexible exchange rates. *Canadian Journal of Economics and Political Science*, 29(4), 475–485. <https://doi.org/10.2307/139336>
- Muth, J. F. (1961). Rational expectations and the theory of price movement. *Econometrica*, 29(3), 315-335
- Nguyen, H. M., Cavoli, T. and Wilson, J. K. (2012). The determinants of inflation in Vietnam. *ASEAN Economic Bulletin*, 29(1), 1-14. doi: 10.1355/ae29-1a
- Özbek, S. and Naimoğlu, M. (2022). Çevre kalitesi-ekonomik karmaşıklık ilişkisi: Türkiye ekonomisi üzerine fourier eşbütünlük analizi. *İstanbul İktisat Dergisi*, 72(1), 407-431. <https://doi.org/10.26650/ISTJECON2022-1061837>
- Özer, M. O. and Gülşen, İ. M. (2025). Türkiye’de asgari ücret ile enflasyon, işsizlik ve büyüme oranları arasındaki ilişki. *Erzurum Teknik Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 21, 71-84.
- Özkök, Y. (2021). Enflasyonu belirleyen faktörler: Türkiye ekonomisi üzerinde yapısal kırılmalı bir analiz. *Artuklu Kaime Uluslararası İktisadi ve İdari Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 4(2), 206-225.
- Perron, P. (1989). The great crash, the oil price shock, and the unit root hypothesis. *Econometrica: Journal of the Econometric Society*, 57(6), 1361-1401.
- Phelps, E. S. (1967) Phillips curves, expectations of inflation and optimal unemployment over time. *Economica*, 34, 254-281. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/2552025>
- Phillips, P. C. and Hansen, B. E. (1990). Statistical inference in instrumental variables regression with I(1) processes. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 57(1), 99-125.
- Saatçioğlu, C. (2005). Türkiye ekonomisindeki enflasyonist sürecin incelenmesine yönelik bir uygulama. *METU Studies in Development*, 32(1), 155-184.
- Sargent, T. (1976). Rational expectations and the theory of economic policy. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 2(2), 169-183.
- Setiartiti, L. and Hapsari, Y. (2019). Determinants of inflation rate in Indonesia. *Jurnal Ekonomi & Studi Pembangunan*, 20(1), 112-123. doi: 10.18196/jesp.20.1.5016
- SSI. (2025). Statistics. Retrieved from <https://www.sgk.gov.tr/Istatistik/Aylik/42919466-593f-4600-937d-1f95c9e252e6>
- Sugözü H. I. and Yaşar, S. (2020). Enflasyon ve faiz ilişkisi: OECD ülkeleri üzerine panel regresyon ve nedensellik analizleri. *Maliye Dergisi*, 179, 85-105.
- Sümer, A. L. (2020). Geleneksel olmayan para politikası kapsamında Neo-Fisher etkisi: 2008 sonrası Türkiye deneyimi. *Uluslararası Ticaret ve Ekonomi Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 4(1), 1-21.
- Taban, S. and Şengür, M. (2016). Türkiye’de enflasyonun kaynağının belirlenmesine yönelik ekonometrik bir analiz. *Erciyes Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakülte Dergisi*, 47, 47-64.
- Taylor, J. B. (1993). Discretion versus policy rules in practice. *Carnegie-Rochester Conference Series on Public Policy*, 39, 195-214. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-2231\(93\)90009-L](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-2231(93)90009-L).
- Taymaz, E., Voyvoda, E. and Yılmaz, K. (2024). Is there a virtuous cycle between wages and productivity? Turkish experience after the transition to democracy. *World Development*, 175, 106474.
- Tayyar, A. E. (2019). Neo-Fisher etkisi ve Türkiye uygulaması. *Uludağ Üniversitesi Fen-Edebiyat Fakültesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 20(36), 307-339.

- Torun, M., Sönmezler, G. and Varol, G. (2024). Para arzı ve beklentilerin Türkiye’de enflasyona etkisi. *Girişimcilik ve Kalkınma Dergisi*, 19(2), 33-41.
- Tuğral, A. and Bari, B. (2021). Asymmetric effects of exchange rate on inflation in Türkiye: What aggregated and disaggregated data reveal. *Erciyes Akademi*, 35(3), 1095–1115.
- TURKSTAT. (2025). Data Portal for Statistics. Retrieved from <https://www.tuik.gov.tr/>
- Varlık, N. and Varlık, S. (2021). Merkez Bankası kredibilitésinin enflasyon oranı üzerindeki asimetrik etkisi- Türkiye örneği. *Journal of Management and Economics Research*, 19(2), 299-319.
- Vazquez, J. F. N. (1956). La evolución del pensamiento económico en el último cuarto de siglo y su influencia en la América Latina. *El Trimestre Económico*, 91(3), 269-283. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23395553>
- Williamson, S. (2016). Neo-Fisherism a radical idea or the most obvious solution to the low-inflation problem? *The Regional Economist, A Quarterly Review of Business and Economic Conditions*, 24(3), 1-24.
- Xu, Y. Liu, Z. X., Chang, H. L., Peculea, A. D. and Su, C. W. (2017). Does self-fulfillment of the inflation expectation exist? *Applied Economics*, 49(11), 1098-1113.
- Yantur, P. (2025). Enflasyon oranının ekonomik belirleyicileri: Türkiye için bir analiz. *Journal of Emerging Economies and Policy*, 10(1), 630-640.
- Yılancı, V. (2010). Fisher hipotezinin Türkiye için sınanması: doğrusal olmayan eşbütünleşme analizi. *Atatürk Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Dergisi*, 23(4), 205-213.
- Yılancı, V., İslamoğlu, E., Yıldırım, S. and Candan, G. (2020). The relationship between unemployment rates and renewable energy consumption: evidence from Fourier ADL cointegration test. *Alphanumeric Journal*, 8(1), 17-28. <https://doi.org/10.17093/alphanumeric.669380>
- Yüksel, C. (2013). Yapısalcı iktisat ve mali uyum. Yayınlanmamış doktora tezi, Ankara Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Maliye Anabilim Dalı, Ankara. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/304179744>
- Zivot, E. and Andrews, D. (1992). Further evidence of great crash, the oil price shock and unit root hypothesis. *Journal of Business and Economic Statistics*, 10, 251-70.